

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Sl. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	120	51
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	123	59
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	191	54
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	174	60
5.	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	178	47
6.	<i>m</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	181	52
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	249	54
8.	<i>o</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	152	61
9.	<i>m</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	149	68
10.	<i>p</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	181	80

* All compounds showed correct results of elemental analysis for nitrogen.

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Synthesis of some Derivatives of Diaryl-substituted Pyrazole and Isoxazole and Substituted Chromenopyrazoline and Chromenoisoxazoline

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PYRAZOLE and isoxazole derivatives possess diverse biological activities¹. In view of these important medicinal properties, we report here the synthesis of some new derivatives 4-benzoyloxy-2-hydroxy-dibenzoylmethane² (**1**) has been condensed separately with hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and hydroxyl-

amine (Scheme 1). The product of condensation with hydrazine has been shown to be **2** from nmr data, which showed nine protons in the aromatic region of which the sharp singlet at δ 7.05 correspond to pyrazole ring proton. There were no signals from the benzoyl moiety which is presumed to have undergone hydrolysis. The structure was supported by mass spectral data which showed peaks at m/z 252, 135, 103 and 77.

The phenyl hydrazine condensation product **3** retained the benzoic ester moiety, and its structure has been deduced from ir and mass spectral data, m/z 180. The isoxazole derivatives (**4**) might be a mixture of two regioisomers **4a** and **4b**, or only one of these, but it could not be established. The mass spectrum of the compound showed peaks at m/z 105 corresponding to C₆H₅CO⁺ and at m/z 137 corresponding to dihydroxy benzoyl cation which can only originate from **4a** and **4b**. 4,4'-Dimethoxy-2'-hydroxychalcone (**5**), prepared from resacetophenone-4-methyl ether, was also condensed with hydrazine and hydroxylamine to give the corresponding pyrazoline (**6**) and dihydroisoxazole (**7**).

In the pyrazoline derivative (**6**), the aliphatic protons formed an ABX pattern with AB part appearing as 8 lines centred at δ 3.4 while the X part appeared as 3 lines centred at δ 4.8. The mass spectrum showed besides the molecular ion peak at m/z 298, prominent peaks at m/z 191, 175, 150, 149 and 134.

In the isoxazole derivative (**7**) the aliphatic protons formed an AMX pattern giving three one-proton double-doublets centred at δ 2.7, 3.6 and 5.0. The mass spectrum showed besides M^+ peak at 299, prominent peaks at m/z 282, 134 and 121. 3-Carboethoxy-7,8-dimethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (**8**), made from gallacetophenone dimethyl ether and diethyl carbonate in the presence of sodium, was also condensed separately with hydrazine hydrate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The product from the former was formulated as **9** incorporating a chromone moiety and a fused pyrazolone moiety. The product from hydroxylamine condensation was formulated as **10** having a chromone moiety and a fused isoxazolone system. Both the structures have been supported by nmr and ir data. The ir spectra showed a chromone carbonyl at 1605 and 1620 cm⁻¹ respectively in compounds **9** and **10**.

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 270-30 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol JNM-FX100 FT spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D300 spectrometer. Tlc was performed in TEF (toluene-ethyl formate-formic acid, 5 : 4 : 1). Micro-analysis data were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values.

4-Benzoyloxy-2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (**1**): Resacetophenone dibenzoate² (3.0 g) dissolved in

Scheme 1

dry toluene (20 ml) containing ignited anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g), was stirred at 110° for 3 h under anhydrous conditions and left overnight at room temperature. The contents were then poured over cold dilute HCl (20% ; 100 ml) and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-methylene chloride mixture as yellow needles (1.5 g), m.p. $168-70^\circ$; gave brownish red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 6.80 (1H, s, enolic olefinic proton), 6.90 (1H, b, H-3) and 7.5-8.2 (12H, m, remaining ArH); m/z 360 (M^+), 241, 106 and 105.

3,5-Diarylpyrazole (2) from 1: A mixture of β -diketone (1; 360 mg), sodium acetate (400 mg), dry benzene (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.2 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. After adding ethanol (4 ml) the mixture was refluxed for another 5 h. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue poured over ice-cold water (30 ml) to give a buff-coloured solid, which was filtered and crystallised from petrol-methylene chloride mixture to give a grey coloured solid (200 mg), m.p. $180-82^\circ$; gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 6.38 (2H, b, H-3,5), 7.05 (1H, s, pyrazole-H), 7.52 (1H, d, H-6), 7.4 (3H, m) and 7.8 (2H, m); m/z 252 (M^+), 135, 103 and 77.

3,5-Diaryl-1-phenylpyrazole (3) from 1: A mixture of β -diketone (1; 300 mg), ethanol (10 ml), phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (200 mg) and

distilled glacial acetic acid (0.6 ml) was refluxed on a boiling water bath for 4 h. The cold reaction mixture was diluted with water (10 ml) and refluxed again for 1 h and then left at room temperature. The resulting red solid was crystallised from methanol as pale yellow crystals (100 mg), m.p. $162-64^\circ$; gave brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 6.7 (1H, s, pyrazole-H), 7.2 (5H, s) and 7.2-8.2 (14H, m); m/z 432 (M^+), 328, 299, 180 and 103.

3,5-Diarylisoaxazoles (5a, 5b) from 1: A mixture of β -diketone (1; 340 mg), ethanol (10 ml), dry pyridine (1 ml) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (120 mg) was refluxed on a boiling water bath for 8 h under anhydrous condition. The solvent was then evaporated and the resulting dry residue was crystallised from methanol-methylene chloride mixture as brownish crystals (100 mg), m.p. $210-12^\circ$; gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 6.9 (2H, m, H-3,5), 7.35 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.5-7.9 (10H, m) and 8.1 (1H, m, H-6); m/z 357 (M^+), 253 and 105.

3-(2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-p-methoxyphenyl-2-pyrazoline (6) from chalcone (5): A mixture of chalcone (5; 600 mg), sodium acetate (800 mg), ethanol (20 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.3 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. Dry benzene (10 ml) was then added to it and refluxed for another 3 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue poured into ice

cold water (50 ml). The resulting yellow solid was crystallised from methanol-methylene chloride mixture as cream coloured crystals (400 mg), m.p. 162°–64°; gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 3.78 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 3.4 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.8 (1H, m, CH), 6.4 (2H, m, H-3,5), 6.85 (2H, d, J 9 Hz H-3',5'), 7.03 (1H, d, H-6) and 7.25 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-2',6'); m/z 298 (M^+), 191, 175, 150, 149 and 134.

3-(2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-p-methoxyphenyl-4-isoxazoline (7) from chalcone (5): A mixture of chalcone (5; 300 mg), ethanol (7.0 ml), dry pyridine (4.0 ml) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (200 mg) was refluxed for 8 h and left overnight at room temperature. It was again refluxed for another 2 h. After evaporating the solvent the residue was poured in ice-cold water (30 ml). The resulting green solid was crystallised from methanol as light grey crystals (200 mg), m.p. 143–44°; gave violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 3.77 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.7 (1H, dd), 3.6 (1H, dd), 5.0 (1H, dd), 6.5 (2H, m, H-3,5), 6.97 (2H, d, H-3',5'), 7.40 (2H, d, H-2',6'), 7.75 (1H, d, H-6) and 8.1 (1H, s, OH); m/z 299 (M^+), 282, 134 and 121.

3-Carboethoxy-4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxy coumarin (8): A solution of gallacetophenone dimethyl ether (1.0 g) dissolved in dry and distilled diethyl carbonate (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h in presence of pulverised sodium (1 g). The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the excess sodium was destroyed by adding methanol (25 ml). Water (75 ml) was then added and unreacted products removed from aqueous layer by extraction with ether. Aqueous layer was acidified with HCl (40 ml) and the resulting reddish brown solid was washed with a little ice-cold water, dried and crystallised from methanol as light brown needles (400 mg), m.p. 170–72°; gave red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl); δ 1.4 (t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 4.0 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.5 (q, J 7 Hz, CH_2O), 7.05 (d, J 8 Hz, H-6), 7.90 (d, J 8 Hz, H-5), 15 (s, 1H, OH); m/z 294 (M^+), 248, 181 and 180.

4-Oxo-4H-chromeno-(2,3-c)-pyrazoline-5-one (9) from 8: 3-Carboethoxy-7,8-dimethoxy-4-hydroxy-coumarin (8; 100 mg) was added to a mixture of sodium acetate (300 mg), methanol (15 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.5 ml). The mixture were refluxed for 12 h on a boiling water bath. Methanol was then evaporated and the residue poured in ice-cold water (50 ml). The resulting buff coloured solid was washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from methanol as light yellow solid (60 mg), m.p. 235–37°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1660 cm^{-1} (amide C=O) and 1605 cm^{-1} (chromone C=O); δ (CDCl_3 + one drop of TFA), 4.05 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.2 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-b), 8.05 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-a).

4-Oxo-4-H-chromeno(2,3-c)-isoxazoline-5-one (10) from 8: 3-Carboethoxy-4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxy coumarin (8; 100 mg) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride

(250 mg) and dry pyridine (0.5 ml) for 14 h on a boiling water bath. Ethanol was then evaporated and the residue poured in ice-cold water (50 ml). The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-methylene chloride mixture as light pink amorphous compound (80 mg), m.p. 225–27°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1670 cm^{-1} (amide C=O) and 1620 cm^{-1} (chromone C=O); δ (CDCl_3 + one drop of TFA) 4.05 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.25 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-b) and 8.10 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-a).

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Substituted-1,8-naphthyridines. Part-XVI. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some New 3-(5-Aryl/Arylamino-1,3,4- oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8- naphthyridines

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MANY 1,8-naphthyridine derivatives exhibit biological activities¹. Hence, it was thought that a 1,8-naphthyridine system, if coupled to oxadiazole moiety, another pharmacophore, the resulting compound might have considerable biological potency. Encouraged by the reports and in continuation of our search for biologically active substituted-1,8-naphthyridines², we report herein the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new 3-(5-aryl/arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines.

The starting compounds, 2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid hydrazide (1), its arylidene derivatives (5) and 4-aryl-1-[(2-methyl-1,8-naphthy-